

TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES AS A SECOND LANGUAGE IN THE EXAMPLE OF ENGLISH

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ANNOTATION: The article examines issues related to the problems of teaching English as a second foreign language. The studied process is complex and requires taking into account the students' linguistic experience and relying on a comparative analysis of the languages contacted during the educational process: English, German and Uzbek (mother tongue). This process can be called developing educational multilingualism, characterized by the manifestation of interference and transfer. In order to eliminate the latter and improve the learning process, it is necessary to study the linguistic phenomena of the two languages in a comparative manner. By identifying the similarities and differences between the two languages, the teacher will be able to optimize the teaching of the second foreign language.

Keywords: English, second language, teaching methodology, society, student.

Introduction. Teaching two or more foreign languages has become an urgent requirement of modern society, because one foreign language is not always enough given the high mobility and sociability of most of the world's population. Over the past decades, English has taken the place of the world language, without which it is impossible to imagine many areas of human life, including the global network - the Internet. Therefore, in all educational institutions, both in secondary general education schools and in higher educational institutions, two or more foreign languages are taught in accordance with the curricula. Being a rather laborious process, teaching two or more languages requires a foreign language teacher to have a different attitude and approach to the learning process.

The subject of the study is ways to improve the effectiveness of the methodological system of teaching English as a second foreign language based on the use of transposition, limiting the interference of the first foreign and Uzbek languages.

Literary review and methodology: The purpose of the work is to explore the process of teaching two foreign languages - English and German, which, in our opinion, should be based on a comparative analysis of the languages being studied, the results of which form the basis of the educational process and help teachers coordinate their work and achieve positive results.

The similarities and differences in the phonetic, lexical and grammatical systems of the languages studied in parallel not only help students to better understand and assimilate the studied linguistic phenomena and processes, but also contribute to the development of linguistic conjecture, broadening their horizons and increasing motivation. Comparative study of two foreign languages is also useful for a deeper understanding of linguistic phenomena and processes occurring in the Uzbek and native languages of students.

“Each language should be considered as something completely self-sufficient, and only then, for methodological purposes, to facilitate mutual learning, one can compare two language systems” [6, p. 318]. According to many scientists [V.D. Arakin O.S. Akhmanova, V.G. Gak, V.N.

Yartseva, R.Yu. Badger, L.S. Barkhudarov and others], the inclusion of a comparative analysis in the process of teaching two or more foreign languages helps to accelerate and deepen the process of understanding, memorizing and automating the language and speech skills and abilities of students.

The use of comparative analysis for linguo-didactic purposes requires, first of all, to determine methodologically relevant similarities and differences between the compared languages. Then it is necessary to determine the type of interlingual interference, and what difficulties may arise as a result of interlingual differences. At the final stage, it becomes necessary to create a system of exercises based on interlingual comparison as a method of teaching a non-native language.

Comparison of the studied languages for didactic purposes allows the teacher to identify the difficulties associated with the features of languages of different systems and find ways to overcome the difficulties. In addition, for learners of a second or third foreign language, such a teaching aid is required, which would be based on the results of a comparative analysis, and take into account the differences and similarities of the languages being studied, which should be reflected in the system of exercises and the presentation of the material.

Theoretical issues of the simultaneous teaching of two or more foreign languages are dealt with by “multilinguodidactics, i.e. theory of teaching multilingualism, the subject of which is the study of optimal methods, techniques, ways of teaching several foreign languages simultaneously or sequentially in different conditions and for different learning purposes” [3].

Baryshnikov N.V. defines the principles of teaching multilingualism, which are the basis for the professional training of a modern multilingual linguist as follows:

- the principle of integrative teaching of several languages;
- the principle of co-learning several languages;
- the principle of relying on the linguistic and educational experience of students;
- the principle of the cognitive orientation of the process of teaching a foreign language;
- the principle of intercultural orientation of the process of teaching a foreign language, etc. [4].

The assimilation of a foreign language by students does not occur spontaneously, like the assimilation of a native language, but is carried out in an organized manner, in three stages - preschool education (kindergarten), school education (junior, middle and senior general education schools) and university. Unlike the native language, a foreign language represents a certain social, cultural and cognitive reality for students, with which students do not have the opportunity to constantly contact. Therefore, many scientists define this type of multilingualism as an artificial emerging educational multilingualism [5]. One of the main requirements of the methodology has always been the creation of natural situations for foreign language communication in various ways in the classroom. However, at present, widely using multimedia and technical teaching aids, the teacher has the opportunity to create an authentic language environment in a foreign language class.

Discussion and results. The process of learning two or more languages is complex and difficult. Costly, because the study of the first foreign language is always based on the transfer of certain language and speech skills and abilities from the native language. This phenomenon in some cases produces a positive effect (the phenomenon of transfer), but in most cases it brings negative results (the phenomenon of interference), and interferes with the correct perception of linguistic material. As for the second foreign language, the skills and abilities acquired by students in the study of the first foreign language, as well as the linguistic experience formed by students on the basis of their native language, have a double influence on it. When learning a foreign language, there is such a phenomenon as transposition. Transposition is a positive transfer of knowledge, skills and abilities of students in their native language to the target language, and the use of existing linguistic experience in the course of foreign language classes, while not causing violations of its norms in the target language [2].

In addition to transfer, with the simultaneous teaching of two languages, there is interference, which manifests itself in violation of the norms of a foreign language under the influence of linguistic phenomena of the native or other language being studied. The more differences between language systems, the more often interference is observed.

The phenomenon of interference is observed in the process of teaching phonetics, vocabulary, grammar - language skills, and in the process of teaching speech skills and abilities - listening, reading, writing, speaking. In addition, interference often manifests itself at the sociocultural level due to insufficiently deep knowledge of the cultural characteristics of the country of the language being studied.

Realities similar in different cultures, phenomena, norms of behavior, for example, unequal forms of speech etiquette, can cause interference. So in Uzbek "please" is used as a politeness formula, meaning "nothing", used as an answer to "thank you". In English and German, "please" and "bitte" do not have these meanings. In English, the word "please" has several variants, depending on the situation: Not at all. - please (not worth it); Here you are. Please (when something is given away), Please is used in a polite request.

The process of learning the phonetic structure of the English language is often hampered by the influence of German. Such a phonetic phenomenon as a hard attack (Glottal Stop), characteristic of the German language, and absent in English, is observed in the speech of students not only at the initial stage of education, and requires considerable effort on the part of the teacher. In addition, students' speech is characterized by deafening of voiced consonants (Devoicing of Voiced consonants); non-observance of the longitude of vowels (Long and short vowels); replacement of interdental sounds (Interdentals) with similar sounds [t] [d].

Lexical interference is the use of foreign language vocabulary in dialogic or monologue speech in the native or first foreign language. When learning English as a second foreign language on the basis of the first language - German, the source of interference, as a rule, is the first foreign language. Some lexical units of foreign languages are very similar, therefore, under similar conditions for mastering lexemes, the probability of such interference is high. For example, the German verb Bekommen (to receive) by analogy with the English verb to become

(become) acquires the meaning of becoming in the speech of students. In the two studied languages, there are a number of lexemes that completely coincide in terms of the volume of meanings. These are the names of the days of the week, the names of the months, the seasons, some numerals, some verbs, etc.

For example: English German

Monday Montag - dushanba;

Winter Winter - qish;

May Mai - may;

four vier - to'rt;

Hundred hundert - yuz;

to dance to dance - o'ynamoq;

The specified layer of vocabulary does not require time and special explanation, and is easily memorized by students.

In addition to errors caused by the interfering influence of the German and Uzbek languages, the phenomenon of intralinguistic interference is observed in the English speech of students. It is possible to single out a fairly large number of groups of lexical units, within which erroneous semantization occurs due to the proximity of the sound and spelling of words. For example: live - leave; live - life; bed - bad; fall-feel; wonder-wander; hungry - angry; angry-agree; snack-snake; like-lick; mouse - mouth; lie - lay; and etc.

The grammatical phenomena of the second foreign language also require comparison with the already known phenomena of the first foreign language. When teaching English on the basis of the first German, i.e. two Germanic languages, students can quite easily memorize the forms of regular and irregular English verbs by analogy with strong and weak German verbs. For example, the English verb to have -had -had corresponds to the German verb haben - hattegehabt (to have, own something).

For example, comparing the English verb to be and the German sein, it will not be difficult for students to remember the forms, understand the meaning of this verb and its functions.

Mastering several foreign languages is not an isolated process, but an interrelated and interdependent simultaneous learning of languages, based on the results of a comparative analysis of languages and on the linguistic experience of students.

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